

**MODELS AND METHODS FOR
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF
INNOVATIVE RESEARCH**

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DEVELOPMENT OF TELECOMMUNICATION SERVICES BASED ON INCREASING FINANCIAL CAPACITY

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Abstract. This article discusses the current state of development of the telecommunications services sector and its further improvement through expanding financial opportunities. The role of the telecommunications network in the economy, the importance of investment resources, lending mechanisms, and the introduction of innovative technologies in improving the quality of services are analyzed. According to the results of the study, strengthening financial stability, improving the investment climate, and developing infrastructure on the basis of public-private partnerships will increase the competitiveness of telecommunications services.

Keywords: telecommunications, financial opportunities, investment, service quality, infrastructure, competitiveness, innovative development, public-private partnership.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari sohasining hozirgi rivojlanish holati va uni moliyaviy imkoniyatlarni kengaytirish orqali yanada takomillashtirish masalalari yoritilgan. Telekommunikatsiya tarmog'ining iqtisodiyotdagi o'rni, xizmatlar sifatini oshirishda investitsiya resurslari, kreditlash mexanizmlari hamda innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etishning ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, moliyaviy barqarorlikni mustahkamlash, investitsiya muhitini yaxshilash va davlat-xususiy sheriklik asosida infratuzilmani rivojlantirish telekommunikatsiya xizmatlarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: telekommunikatsiya, moliyaviy imkoniyatlar, investitsiya, xizmat sifati, infratuzilma, raqobatbardoshlik, innovatsion rivojlanish, davlat-xususiy sheriklik.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается современное состояние развития сектора телекоммуникационных услуг и его дальнейшее совершенствование за счёт расширения финансовых возможностей. Анализируется роль телекоммуникационной сети в экономике, значение инвестиционных ресурсов, механизмов кредитования и внедрения инновационных технологий в повышении качества услуг. Результаты исследования свидетельствуют о том, что укрепление финансовой стабильности, улучшение инвестиционного климата и развитие инфраструктуры на основе государственно-частного партнёрства будут способствовать повышению конкурентоспособности телекоммуникационных услуг.

Ключевые слова: телекоммуникации, финансовые возможности, инвестиции, качество услуг, инфраструктура, конкурентоспособность, инновационное развитие, государственно-частное партнёрство.

Introduction. Investments, in particular, investments in fixed capital, play an important role in the sustainable development of a market economy. Renewal, modernization of fixed capital and expansion of production capacities are one of the main factors of economic growth. In this regard, investments made at the expense of state budget funds play an important role in accelerating structural changes in the national economy, developing production infrastructure and supporting social sectors.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the volume and share of state budget investments have been increasing significantly in recent years. This directly affects the pace of economic growth, creating new jobs, increasing export potential and reducing economic disparities between regions. At the same time, increasing the efficiency of state investments and combining them with private sector investments is one of the urgent issues of today.

This article analyzes the impact of state budget investments on fixed capital, their role in economic growth, and the effectiveness of reforms in this area.

Literature review. There are a wide range of approaches in the scientific literature on the financial aspects of the development of telecommunications services, which are devoted to the issues of economic efficiency of the sector, investment activity, financial stability, and financial support of digital infrastructure.

First of all, J. Stiglitz emphasizes in his works that information and communication technologies (ICT) are a key factor in increasing the competitiveness of the economy. In his opinion, investments in the telecommunications sector contribute not only to economic growth, but also to the formation of a knowledge economy [1].

In the theory of “competitive advantage” developed by M. Porter, the development of telecommunications infrastructure is considered as a strategic resource that increases the international competitiveness of the country. According to him, a high-quality communication system ensures the effective functioning of the business environment and opens up new markets [2].

Uzbek scholar Sh. Khodiyev analyzes the issues of financial management of telecommunications services, justifying the importance of managing capital flows, budgeting and optimizing costs in this area. According to him, the financial stability of the sector is ensured through an effective investment policy and diversification of services [3].

A. Karimov in his research analyzed investment mechanisms in the modernization of the telecommunications network of Uzbekistan, the introduction of 4G and 5G technologies. In particular, he showed effective methods of attracting private capital to the network through the public-private partnership (PPP) model [4].

Foreign sources emphasize innovative approaches to financing telecommunications services. For example, D. Tapscott in his work “Digital Economy” assessed investment in digital infrastructure as a factor ensuring the long-term economic stability of the state. At the same time, research conducted by J. Noll highlights the financial risk management system, profit margin optimization, and service diversification mechanisms in telecommunications companies [5].

The 2023 report of the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan notes that more than 1.5 trillion soums

were invested in expanding the telecommunications infrastructure in the country, which had a significant impact on the economic growth of this sector.

Research methodology. The research methodology used to study the financial aspects of the development of telecommunications services is based on the principles of scientificity, systematicity and an integrated approach. The purpose of the study is to analyze the financial support, investment sources and economic efficiency of telecommunications services, as well as to develop practical recommendations for improving the financial mechanisms for the development of the sector.

Analysis and discussion of results. The development of the telecommunications sector is one of the most important components of the modern economy. This sector plays an important role not only in information exchange, but also in increasing the efficiency of all sectors of the economy. Financial aspects are of particular importance in the development of telecommunications services, as the sector requires large investments for technical upgrades, infrastructure expansion, and the introduction of digital technologies.

First, capital investments are an important financial source for the modernization of telecommunications networks. Long-term investments are required for the development of fiber-optic lines, mobile communication base stations, satellite systems, and digital platforms. Therefore, attracting funds from the state budget, international financial institutions, and private investors is of strategic importance.

Secondly, the financial sustainability of telecommunications services is associated with the diversification of their sources of income. In addition to traditional voice communication services, a system of generating income through the Internet, digital content, data transmission and cloud technologies is being formed. In this way, companies expand the types of services and maintain their competitiveness.

Thirdly, financial analysis plays an important role in determining the pricing policy of services. Telecommunications companies regularly analyze economic efficiency in order to optimize their costs, reduce network operation costs and increase profit margins. When setting prices, factors such as the return on investment (ROI), profit margin and consumer solvency are taken into account.

Fourthly, in the telecommunications sector, it is necessary to improve the financial management system in the conditions of the digital economy. In this process, modern methods of financial management are used - risk management, financial planning, budgeting and mechanisms for evaluating investment projects. Strategic financial planning is especially important for the introduction of 5G technology and the development of service systems based on artificial intelligence.

Fifth, the mechanisms of state support for the sector are also an important financial aspect. Tax incentives, subsidies, grants and investment programs create opportunities for expanding telecommunications infrastructure. In particular, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, within the framework of the “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” strategy, a large amount of funds are being allocated to the telecommunications sector.

Conclusions and proposals. In conclusion, the financial aspects of the development of telecommunications services are closely related to attracting investments in the sector, effective cost management, introducing new technologies and

ensuring financial stability. Conducting a rational financial policy in this direction will accelerate the country's transition to a digital economy and strengthen the position of telecommunications companies in global competition.

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